

ISic2918

I.Sicily inscription 2918

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1 : mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2 : mm

Text

1. Ἡσύχις λιμενάρ

2. χης

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1950

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645307

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1950-1951. Christiana-Byzantina Siciliae II. *Nuovo Didaskaleion*. 4: 55-66. At 10 no.11

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 41 n.199

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 581 fig.16

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